

HIGH-FREQUENCY ERRORS OF AN ELECTRIC-FIELD METER
IN COMPLICATED ENVIRONMENTS

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ABSTRACT

We report the results of a study of electric-field-meter (EFM) errors in complex electromagnetic environments. Two types of errors are considered -- errors in the measured electric field for a common EFM design, and errors in the assumption of equal electric and magnetic energy densities in a multiple-plane-wave environment. Typical errors in both cases are approximately one-half to three dB, but in some circumstances they can exceed 10 dB.

I. INTRODUCTION

Electric-field meters (EFM's) are typically calibrated using single-frequency, single-source standard fields; but in practice they are not always used in such simple environments, and their response to more complex fields can be different than for the calibrating fields. We have recently completed a study of EFM errors in multiple-source and/or frequency (MSF) environments, and this paper summarizes the results. Further detail can be found in [1]. The analysis concentrated on new errors peculiar to complex environments and not previously analyzed. It also was restricted almost exclusively to periodic fields with periods of about 10^{-6} s or less, much shorter than the time scale ($\sim 10^{-4}$ s) set by the probe considered.

The MSF errors can be divided into two classes. There are errors in the average and/or peak electric field actually read by the meter when the field being measured does not have a simple sinusoidal time dependence. We investigated these meter errors for a common probe configuration consisting of electrically short dipole antennas with diode loads, connected to the metering unit by an RF filter transmission line. In addition, there are what could be called errors of inference. These are user, rather than meter, errors. Although EFM's measure electric fields only, they are sometimes used as hazard meters or energy-density meters. In such applications one assumes that the magnetic field energy density is equal to the measured electric field energy density, as is the case for a monochromatic plane wave. For other field configurations this equality does not hold, and the inferred electromagnetic (EM) energy density is incorrect.

The present investigation addresses both types of errors and determines typical and extreme magnitudes in each case. The next section deals with the EFM errors, and the energy-density errors are treated in Section III. The final section contains a brief summary.

II. ELECTRIC FIELD MEASUREMENT ERRORS

We consider first the errors in the electric field actually measured. The type of EFM we have analyzed is a common (see e.g., ref. [2]) configuration exemplified by, but not restricted to, the NBS EFM-5 [3]. (When specific values of meter parameters were needed, those of the EFM-5 were used. The qualitative results, however, apply to any meter sharing the same design.) The meter consists of a short dipole antenna with a diode detector as a probe, with a transmission line connecting it to the box contain-

ing the metering electronics. The transmission line itself is a distributed RF filter in order to avoid perturbing the ambient field. The response of the electronics in the metering unit is assumed to be unaffected by the external field. For an isotropic probe, three orthogonal dipole antennas are used, each with its own independent transmission line within the cable joining probe and box.

Because the dipole antennas are short compared to the wavelengths of the radiation being measured, the electric field does not vary significantly over the volume of the probe, so that it effectively is sensitive to the electric field at a single point as a function of time, $\vec{E}(\vec{x} = 0, t)$. An important consequence follows immediately: for meter errors the number of sources is immaterial, and all that matters is the temporal waveform of the electric field at the probe position. Only if its time dependence is a single sinusoid is it operating under the calibration conditions. A corollary result is that the presence of reflections does not introduce new MSF errors since they have the same frequency as the field from the primary source and combine with it to yield a net $\vec{E}(\vec{x} = 0, t)$ which is a single sinusoid in time.

When the incident field at the probe position does not have a simple sinusoid for its temporal waveform, errors arise from a collusion of the non-linear response of the diode detector and the filtering effect of the transmission line. The antenna plus diode plus transmission line can be represented by the equivalent circuit of Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Equivalent circuit for a single antenna plus diode, with filter line also indicated.

The filter line is represented only by a black box which is assumed to transmit DC, filter RF, and have little effect on the effective load of the antenna. The input voltage $v_i(t)$ is proportional to the electric field at the antenna position; and an expression for the output voltage $v_o(t)$ can be obtained in terms of the input voltage and three parameters of the antenna-diode combination. The three parameters are an effective time constant (a^{-1}) and two voltage scales (b^{-1} , α^{-1}), which for the EFM-5 have the values

$$a = 33.8 \text{ kHz}, b = 4.22 \text{ V}^{-1}, \alpha = 38 \text{ V}^{-1}. \quad (1)$$

Provided the input signal is periodic, with period (p) short compared to a^{-1} , $a \cdot p \ll 1$, the voltage across the diode can be written

$$v_d(t) \cong \frac{b\tilde{v}_i(t)}{\alpha} - \frac{1}{\alpha} \ln \left\{ \frac{1}{p} \int_0^p e^{b\tilde{v}_i(t')} dt' \right\} \quad (2)$$

$$\tilde{v}_i(t) \equiv v_i(t) - \langle v_i \rangle.$$

Note that the argument of the logarithm is time-independent, which is not true at lower frequencies. The effect of the filter line then is to remove the RF components of $v_d(t)$, resulting in an output signal of

$$v_o(t) \cong -\frac{1}{\alpha} \ln \left\{ \int_0^1 e^{b\tilde{v}_i(t=xp)} dx \right\} \quad (3)$$

In the limiting cases of small or large incident fields ($b|\tilde{v}_i|_{\max} \ll 1$ and $b|\tilde{v}_i|_{\max} \gg 1$ respectively) the output voltage assumes the simple forms

$$v_o \cong -\frac{b^2}{2\alpha} \langle \tilde{v}_i^2 \rangle \quad \text{small } |E_i|,$$

$$\cong -\frac{b}{\alpha} \tilde{V}_i \quad \text{large } |E_i|, \quad (4)$$

where $\tilde{V}_i$ is the peak value of $\tilde{v}_i(t)$. These are the usual square-law and linear regimes; the crucial point is that the square-law and linear dependences are on different variables. For small incident fields the signal reaching the meter is directly proportional to the average of $(E_i - \langle E_i \rangle)^2$, and completely insensitive to the peak value, whereas for large incident fields the opposite is true.

The origin of multiple source and frequency (MSF) errors is now apparent. Since it was calibrated using a single sinusoid, the meter responds to the signal of (3) by finding the magnitude of the sinusoid which would result in $v_o(t)$. It implicitly solves

$$-\frac{1}{\alpha} \ln \left[\int_0^1 e^{bV \cos(2\pi x)} dx \right] = v_o(t)$$

$$= -\frac{1}{\alpha} \ln \left[\int_0^1 e^{b\tilde{v}_i(xp)} dx \right] \quad (5)$$

for V , and reads $v_{\text{peak}}(\text{meter}) = V$, $\langle v^2 \rangle_{\text{meter}} = V^2/2$. For a general waveform, therefore, the meter will not be correct on both peak and average readings. Since $v_o(t)$ is constant, the meter receives only one piece of information, which is insufficient to determine two independent quantities. From the limiting forms of (4), we see that only the average reading need be correct for small fields and only the peak reading for large fields (both assuming $\tilde{v}_i = v_i$). For intermediate-magnitude incident fields, neither peak nor average reading need be correct.

The magnitude of the meter error depends on the actual waveform, the field intensity, and whether the peak or average is being measured. We have used eqs. (3) and (5) to calculate the error for a variety of different waveforms, and display the results in figures 2-4. In each case Δ_{avg} , the dB error in the average E^2 , is plotted as a function of incident field strength. For a waveform like a narrow pulse the error in the measured peak or average intensity

can be as large as 10 dB, but more typical values are on the order of 2 dB. We also investigated the case of various numbers of randomly distributed sources with different intensities and frequencies, finding that the average meter error was around 2-4 dB, but that the maximum possible errors were much larger.

Fig. 2. Error in average electric field intensity for $E_i(t) = E_i^{\text{rms}} (\cos \omega t + \cos 2 \omega t)$. Error in peak intensity is given by $\Delta_{\text{pk}} = \Delta_{\text{avg}} - 3$ dB.

Fig. 3. Error in average electric field intensity for a periodic square wave, $\pm E_i^{\text{rms}}$. In this case $\Delta_{\text{pk}} = \Delta_{\text{avg}} + 3$ dB.

Fig. 4. Error in average electric field intensity for a periodic square pulse with various ratios of width (δ) to period. Peak value is $E_i^{\text{pk}} = E_i^{\text{rms}} \sqrt{p/\delta}$. The error in the peak intensity is given by $\Delta_{\text{pk}} - \Delta_{\text{avg}} = -10$ dB, -7 dB, -4 dB for $\delta/p = 0.05$, 0.1 , and 0.2 respectively.

A few qualifications and clarifications of these results should be noted. The first point is that our analysis is only valid for incident fields with periods which are short relative to a certain characteristic time scale of the antenna plus diode. For longer-period signals--including those with only

high-frequency Fourier components, such as AM radio--our analysis does not apply. In addition, even for short periods, it is quite possible with the EFM configuration considered here to choose the meter parameters such that one is always effectively in the large-field domain or always in the small-field region; and therefore it is possible for the meter to measure accurately either the peak field or the average field squared, even for complex, multifrequency fields. It is not, however, possible to measure both peak and average with a single probe of this configuration, and meters which try to do so will err on one or the other (or both) at any given field strength.

III. ENERGY DENSITY INFERENCE ERRORS

Meters which only measure either the electric or the magnetic field cannot measure the true total electromagnetic field energy density. That requires simultaneous measurement of both electric and magnetic fields, as can be done, for example, with a probe developed recently for near-field measurements [4]. In order to infer a total energy density from a measurement of either the electric or magnetic field intensity, some relationship between electric and magnetic energy densities must be assumed. The assumption usually made is that the two are equal, as is true for a single plane wave. This section considers the errors involved in that assumption.

We define

$$\Delta(E/H) = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{2 u_E}{u_{tot}} \right) = 10 \log_{10} \left[\frac{2 |\bar{E}|^2}{|\bar{E}|^2 + \frac{\mu}{\epsilon} |\bar{H}|^2} \right] \quad (6)$$

where u_E and u_{tot} are the electric-field and total energy densities respectively. It is clear that this "error" is a property of the environment and not of the meter used; in fact we shall assume that the electric field is known exactly. $\Delta(E/H)$ is the dB error made by assuming that $u_{tot} = 2 u_E$. In the near field of an antenna (or reflecting surface), it is well known that this error can be large--e.g. in the near field of an antenna one can find $|\bar{H}|^2/|\bar{E}|^2 \rightarrow \infty$. Such near-field problems are well known, and we shall not labor them. The question we address is the size of $\Delta(E/H)$ when there are a number of plane waves present, i.e. multiple sources and/or reflections, but in the far field of each. The results for these situations are less obvious and less well known.

We have studied the energy density errors, for both peak and average energy density measurements, for numbers of plane wave sources ranging from two to twenty. For more than two sources it is impractical to use anything other than a statistical approach, since the error depends on so many variables--all the relative intensities, phases, polarizations, directions, and frequencies. Accordingly, for each number of sources we have generated 100 or 1000 random configurations (directions, magnitudes, etc.) and computed the average, standard deviation, and extreme values of $\Delta_{pk}(E/H)$ and $\Delta_{avg}(E/H)$, the errors in peak and average energy densities.

For the average energy density, there is no error if no two sources have the same frequency. The errors are largest when all sources have the same frequency, as with multiple reflections for example. Results for all sources having equal frequency are shown in Fig. 5. For each number of sources, 1000 random configurations were generated, and the mean and standard deviation of $\Delta_{avg}(E/H)$ were computed for that ensemble. The typical errors were from -2 dB to +2 dB, but the extremes were -10 to -12 dB and +3 dB. This was true whether the sources were distributed in two or three dimensions.

Fig. 5. Mean, standard deviation, and maximum values of the error $\Delta_{avg}(E/H)$, as functions of the number of sources. For each N_{source} , 1000 random configurations were used.

For the error in the peak energy density we used ensembles of 100 random configurations. (The computation requires considerably more time than that for Δ_{avg} .) Unlike Δ_{avg} , $\Delta_{pk}(E/H)$ is not zero when all the frequencies are different. Fig. 6 contains results for $\Delta_{pk}(E/H)$. The mean of $\Delta_{pk}(E/H)$ tends to be around -0.3 dB with a standard deviation of 0.7 dB or less. If all frequencies are constrained to be equal, the standard deviation increases to around 2 dB.

Fig. 6. Mean, standard deviation, and maximum and minimum values of $\Delta_{pk}(E/H)$, using 100 random configurations for each N_{source} .

IV. SUMMARY

In this paper we have presented salient results of a study of errors related to electric field measurements in complex environments. The section of EFM errors is relevant to users of meters similar to the NBS EFM-5 when more than one Fourier frequency

may be present. The section on energy-density errors applies to anyone using any EFM to indicate total energy or power density in the presence of more than one plane-wave source (including reflections). Details of the calculations as well as further results can be found in [1].

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